

SYNTHESIS OF ENTEROADSORBENT-INTRODUCING Fe AND Al POLYHYDROXYCATION BETWEEN MONTMORILLONITE LAYERS

Jurayeva F.N.
Alikulova H.A.
Boltayeva G.X.

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Tashkent city, Republic of Uzbekistan

e-mail: jurayevaferuza636@gmail.com, phone: (93) 560-34-89

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Efficiency: enterosorbents are substances with a high specific surface area, capable of adsorbing molecules, ions and various particles. They are used in medicine for various purposes, they have antimicrobial and detoxifying properties, for example, the ability to bind to heavy metals and toxins, and they are used in the performance of some complex tasks, such as poisoning models (food poisoning, diarrhea, allergies). Therefore, the synthesis of adsorbents and catalyst carriers, which are absolutely harmless to human health and economically inexpensive, with high adsorption properties, is considered urgent today.

The purpose of the research: to develop methods of optimal enrichment of natural clay minerals for the creation of enteroadsorbents and to determine the composition of enriched samples.

Methods and techniques: Krantau mine bentonite (KP) and Navbahor alkaline bentonite (NIB), which are widespread in our country, were selected as the object of the research. Enrichment of the selected research objects with respect to montmorillonite, the main mineral with high adsorption properties, was carried out as follows: the sample was mixed in distilled water (pH=6.6) and water in a mass ratio of 1:10 to form a suspension of 100 g. In order to convert the calcium bentonite contained in the suspension into its sodium form and precipitate Ca^{2+} and other Me^{2+} ions, Na_2CO_3 was added in the amount of 0.5% of the solid sample mass, the suspension was stirred in a magnetic stirrer for 15 minutes and allowed to stand for 48 hours. Then the suspension was diluted with water in a ratio of 1:5 while stirring. In this process, Ca^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} salts, quartz and other water-insoluble substances with high dispersibility are separated into the sediment. During the first 20 minutes, the upper part of the suspension was separated from the part that had settled by decantation. The resulting suspension was separated from the solid phase by centrifugation. The ion indicators of each stage were determined on the IM-160 device, the obtained results are presented in Figure 1. Information about the structure of enriched clay minerals can be determined by thermal analysis. Simultaneous dynamic thermogravimetric and calorimetric analyzes were obtained using a Setaram Labsys evo apparatus.

Figure 1

Result: As a result of changes in suspension pH values during the enrichment processes, it can be seen that the pH indicators decrease from 8.74 to 7.22 and from 8.68 to 7.95 in KP and NIB samples, respectively. According to the results of synchronous dynamic thermogravimetric calorimetric analyses: (A- KP and B- NIB) thermogravimetric analysis curve (DTGA curves show that intense decomposition took place in KP bentonite between temperatures of 55-157°C and 166-457°C. In NIB, decomposition temperatures correspond to the range

of 63-148°C and 159-417°C. The initial decomposition The amount of mass loss at temperatures (100-150°C) proves that natural clay minerals are rich in sodium montmorillonite.

Conclusion: Based on the analysis of the obtained results, it can be concluded that the change in pH values means that natural bentonites are enriched with the main important mineral montmorillonite due to the decrease in the amount of additional substances. the enrichment method used increases the amount of montmorillonite in the natural clay minerals and increases their adsorption and other colloidal-chemical properties.